

Removal of chromium(VI) in wastewater by adsorption on iron oxide nanoparticles

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Abstract : The nanoparticles are used in various applications because of their narrow size distribution, huge surface area, better compatibility and great adsorption efficiency to various heavy metal ions. In this paper, iron oxide nanoparticles were prepared from low-grade iron ore by coating with ferric chloride. This iron oxide nanoparticles adsorbent was used for the removal of chromium(VI) from aqueous solution in the batch reactor with different conditions such as pH, contact time and heavy metal ion concentration. The adsorption of 37 nm size iron oxide nanoparticles adsorbent was achieved 87% greater adsorption capacity of 10 mg/L solution at 3 pH with the contact time of 5 min. The Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin adsorption isotherm was used to explain the isotherms and isotherm constants. The experimental data were best fitted by Temkin isotherm with 0.99 consistency.

Keywords : Adsorption, iron oxide nanoparticles, chromium(VI), wastewater.

I. Introduction

The chromium (Cr) is an important heavy metals and widely used in many industrial processes such as mining industry, metallurgical industry. It is very toxic, mutagenic and teratogenic substance and causes severe harmful effects on human health including liver damage, severe diarrhea, lung tumors, kidney damage, allergic dermatitis and respiratory problems. The three oxidation states for chromium i.e. Cr^{II}, Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} be present in nature. The Cr^{III} is most stationary, less soluble and stable form, however, Cr^{VI} is highly mobile, soluble, bio-available and major threat to the environment and the species like *hydrogenchromate* (HCrO₄⁻), *chromate* (CrO₄²⁻) and *dichromate* (Cr₂O₇²⁻). The maximum total concentration of chromium in drinking water is less than 0.05 mg/L suggested by WHO (2002) standards¹ and IS 10500 : 2012². The effective treatment of wastewater has become a basic need of all properly functioning societies and a key factor to protect public health^{3,4}. Now, it is required to develop new mate-

rial (adsorbent) with improved characteristics having high efficiency to remove metal toxicity in wastewater. The significance of iron oxide nanoparticles in the field of adsorption offers the efficient removal of heavy metals like Cr^{VI} contaminants. The advent of technology revolutionizes give an opportunity to synthesize nanoparticles ranging from 1 to 100 nm^{5,6}. Iron oxide nanomaterials have property to easy synthesis, easy coating or modification, and ability to control process or manipulate the matter on an atomic scale can give unparalleled versatility^{7,8}. Additionally, the iron oxide nanomaterial has low toxicity, chemical inertness, biocompatibility properties and show a tremendous potential in combination with biotechnology⁹. The aim of this study, to study the adsorption efficiency of Cr^{VI} ion by using iron oxide nanomaterial as an adsorbent.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

The aqueous solution of Cr^{VI} was prepared as per

standard methods (APHA)¹⁰. In this method, 141.4 mg $K_2Cr_2O_7$ was dissolved in water and diluted to 100 ml. The initial concentrations of Cr^{VI} varying from 10 to 50 mg/L.

B. Preparation of sorbent

The preparation of iron oxide nanoparticle involves, low-grade iron ore obtained from iron mines. This iron ore was crushed then coated with ferric chloride. The coated iron ore crushed into powder then treated with various chemicals reagent, to formed iron oxide nanoparticles¹¹.

C. Analytical method

The Cr^{VI} ion concentration in the solution was determined by colorimetric methods as per standard methods (APHA). The series of absorbance of known Cr^{VI} ions concentration present in the solution was determined with the help of standard curve between the absorbance with known Cr^{VI} ion concentration solution.

D. Experimental studies

The batch adsorption was performed by mixing 0.1 g of iron oxide nanoparticles adsorbent to 100 ml of Cr^{VI} solution. The initial concentrations of Cr^{VI} varying from 10 to 50 mg/L at pH 3, room temperature 25°C and shaking rate 200 rpm. The pH was measured by pH meter [MAC MSW-551], and the concentration of metal ions was determined using UV Spectrophotometer [LABINDIA UV3000+].

E. Characterization of sorbent

The iron oxide nanoparticles adsorbent was characterized by : (a) The crystalline nature of prepared adsorbent was analyzed on an advanced X-ray diffractometer with 20°–80° (2 theta) scanning range using Model no. Panalytical X' Pert Pro MRD, (b) The size and morphology of the synthesized iron oxide nanoparticle were characterized by SEM using Model no. Zeiss, SUPRA 40 VP and (c) The sample composition and element contents were analyzed by X-ray EDAX (Model no. Zeiss, SUPRA 40 VP.)

III. Results and discussion

The adsorbent iron oxide nanoparticles characterized by XRD, SEM, and energy dispersive analysis system of X-ray (EDAX). The XRD analysis shows in Fig. 1. The mass of the coating did not cause any measurable change in the phase property of Fe_2O_3 pattern of XRD significantly. The position and relative intensities of diffraction peaks match well with those from the PDF file number 00-001-1053 for hematite (Fe_2O_3).

Fig. 1. XRD analysis of coated iron oxide nanoparticle.

The size and morphology of the synthesized iron oxide nanoparticle characterized by SEM analysis in Fig. 2. From Fig. 2, it revealed that coated iron oxide nanoparticles are nearly spherical in shape and 37 nm in diameter. The compositions and elements contents of the sample were analyzed by energy dispersive analysis system of X-ray EDAX show in Fig. 3. The EDX spectra showed the strong peaks of Fe, O and Cl represented in Table 1. The composition components of coated iron oxide formed by co-precipitation synthesis Fe was 44% and O was 45%. The result demonstrates the purity of the substance.

The batch adsorption experiments were carried out by varying contact time, pH, and adsorbent dose. The equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_e) was evaluated by the equation.

Fig. 2. SEM analysis of coated iron oxide nanoparticle.

Fig. 3. EDAX analysis of coated iron oxide nanoparticle.

Table 1. EDX analysis of coated iron oxide nanoparticle

Elements	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
O	45.39	71.31
Mg	2.94	3.03
Si	3.44	3.08
Cl	1.67	1.18
Ca	2.44	1.53
Fe	44.12	19.86
Total	100	

$$q_e = \frac{V(C_0 - C_e)}{M}$$

where ‘ q_e ’ is the equilibrium adsorption capacity (mg/g), C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium con-

centration of solute in the liquid phase (mg/L), respectively, V is the volume (L) in the liquid phase and W is the amount of adsorbent (g).

The maximum 87% removal of Cr^{VI} at pH 3, temperature 25°C and agitation speed of 200 rpm. The pH test was carried from 2 to 8. At high pH (>4) the colour was not developed due to the interference of ions with diphenylcarbazide. The effect of varying chromium concentration on adsorption rate was studied in the range (10–50 mg/L) at pH 3, temperature 25°C, and 60 min contact time. The result revealed that the percentage of removal decreased with increase in initial chromium concentration. Table 2 shows adsorption parameters for Cr removal by iron oxide nanoparticle.

Table 2. Adsorption parameters for Cr removal

Parametres	Value
Size (nm)	37
pH	3
Equilibrium time (min)	5
Adsorbent (g)	0.1
Metal ion concentration (mg/L)	10
% Removal	87
R^2 (Langmuir)	0.8321
R^2 (Freundlich)	0.9738
R^2 (Temkin)	0.9911

The adsorption isothermal studies were carried out on iron oxide nanoparticle adsorbent under same conditions. The Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 shows in Langmuir, Freundlich and Temkin adsorption iso-

Fig. 4. Langmuir adsorption isotherm for Cr adsorption.

Fig. 5. Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Fig. 6. Temkin adsorption isotherm.

therms. The study indicated the suitability of the adsorbents used for removal of Cr^{VI} and Temkin adsorption isotherm was best fitted and it confirms that the adsorption of Cr^{VI} onto iron oxide nanoparticle follows a chemisorption process.

IV. Conclusion

The present study was carried out to the suitability of a novel indigenous adsorbent, iron oxide nanoparticle prepared from iron ore for the removal

of chromium from the wastewater. The removal efficiency 87% was achieved at 3 pH and 37 nm size by using iron oxide nanoparticle adsorbent. The experimental data were fitted to different isotherm model and the Temkin model was found to be the best model with R^2 value 0.9911.

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